

Transforming Research through Innovative
Practices for Linked Interdisciplinary Exploration

Miro Virtual Whiteboard Documentation of the TRIPLE ThatCamp #1: Discovering Discovery - Envision Your Ideal Research Ecosystem for Exploring Research Resources (11 May 2021)

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Image: „Discovery“ illuminated letters: Photo by [Noble Mitchell](#) on [Unsplash](#) (CC0)

Discovering discovery

Envision your ideal ecosystem for
exploring research resources

The first TRIPLE ThatCamp

11 May 2021

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Welcome to the virtual whiteboard of the first TRIPLE ThatCamp!

It's up to you: Make the ThatCamp YOUR event! Here you can suggest topics you are interested in as well as topics on which you would like to lead a session. The exact agenda will be determined jointly by all participants on the day of the event.

There are three modes of board **navigation**: Mouse, Trackpad, and Touchscreen. Depending on what controls you use, Miro will set the mode that works best. Check [here](#) how to do that (e.g. how to zoom in and out).

You can create a new **sticky note** by double clicking on the corresponding symbol in the left-hand menu bar (fourth symbol from the top:) , by clicking "N" on your keyboard or by choosing "Add sticky note" in the context menu when you do a right click on your mouse.

Here's a [link to Miro's help page](#) and a [link to Miro's YouTube channel](#) if you would like to find out more about how Miro boards work. At the beginning of the event we will also give you a brief tour and explain the main functions that we are going to use.

What is a ThatCamp?

ThatCamp stands for “The Humanities And Technology Camp”. It is a so-called unconference based on the BarCamp concept: an open, agile and spontaneous meeting where participants learn and work together by engaging in group discussions, co-working sessions or other forms of collaborative work. People engage with each other to “create, build, write, hack, and solve problems”.

Learn more about ThatCamps here

and here

thatcamp.org

About | THATCamp

11 May 2021

09:00	Pre-event Technical Check (optional)
9:30-9:45	Opening of ThatCamp
9:45-10:15	Introduction & Warm-Up
10:15-11:15	Session Pitches and Planning
11:15-11:30	<i>Break</i>
11:30-13:00	Sessions I
13:00-14:00	<i>Lunch break</i>
14:00-15:30	Sessions II
15:30-15:45	<i>Break</i>
15:45-16:45	Presentation of Results
16:45-17:00	Wrap Up & Closing of Event

TOPIC IDEAS & WISHES

Which topics relating to the event theme can you think of? What would you like to raise in the discussions? Add your ideas here.

What are the challenges of finding reliable partners online?

How is "discovery service" defined? How does it differ from other types of search database?

What does "to discover" mean a) in general, b) in a research context?

What are downsides and challenges of interdisciplinary discovery services?

Are we missing out on research results obtained outside of the English speaking/publishing world? How can we reach them?

Yes, we are missing all research results from the whole rest of the non-anglophone research publishing world!

What do you find the most difficult aspect of the discovery process?

How much has Open Access and FAIR data contributed to Discovery?

A scientific approach: How Knowledge Discovery from Data and Human Computer Interaction can support discovery. "To enable end users to find and recognize previously unknown and potentially useful and usable information. It may be defined as the process of identifying novel, valid and potentially useful data patterns, with the goal of understanding these data"

How can we make sure that the discovery system is maintained as open source and not "hijacked" by publishers with commercial interests in "user profiles" of researchers or misused as "ranking index" who's research is of "interest"...?!

Are bibliographic data really interoperable? When you talk of research data in Europe you inevitably stumble into the I4R acronym.

Or in other terms, data has to be: Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable. However if you deal with bibliographic data, the most ancient data to be findable and accessible by means of DOI, or Open Public Access Catalogues you may find out that interoperability and reusability are not taken for granted.

Although, there is a wide range of choice of bibliography manager softwares that apparently are supposed to do it for you, in any electronic resource you may find out the "Clear" button on which one can click to easily, and most of the time, directly download your bibliographic reference in one's personal client account in the proprietary or open source platform hosting one's bibliographic data.

But what to do if instead of one reference you have to make some references, or if in some cases the direct link button does not exist? In these cases you can export your data only in the format available for the software chosen and do the upload. What instead of your bibliographic data have been collected in excel format or csv one? In this case, interoperability inevitably clashes with styles in which bibliographic information have been received according to the proprietary or open access managing software importing formats. By convergence also changing is critical to those that store the data software.

The paradox is that the first kind of data that became open access are the one meanings that are less interoperable and sharable.

Research query has anyone a suggestion on how to transform bibliographic data in the form of excel or csv file into importing formats used by main softwares managing references?

Wished result: a Jupyter notebook containing all the script to transform excel and csv files into formats to be importable into softwares managing references

How can you understand what 'open source' means if you know nothing about 'how to produce executable code' and have never tried to produce a 'source code'?

How should we use and benefit from Persistent Identifiers in a research discovery platform?

Is Discovery an individual activity or can it be a collaborative one?

What makes you happy when discovering something?

Is multilingualism important for Discovery?

Was is meant with "Discovery" here? A technology? A search method? An attitude?

matching in profiles discovery : researchers profiles and beyond

Can you discuss Discovery without having chosen a technology / a platform?

How can we "disrupt digital monolingualism" and ensure the discovery of research in non-anglophone languages and scripts?

Who is developing, training and revising the search algorithm(s) for TRIPLE?

What are the main Open Science research resources/platforms currently available for "discovering"?

Matching in profiles discovery: researchers profiles and beyond

Is multilingualism important for Discovery?

How can we better understand how exactly researchers are using discovery systems (more participative empirical research needed!)

How can we better be aware of the "bias" of discovery algorithms? (with regard to language, scripts, classification vocabulary etc.)

how do we improve peer review reports which are fundamental for discovery?

Famous quote by Donald Rumsfeld 'There are known knowns. These are things we know that we know. There are known unknowns. That is to say, there are things that we know we don't know. But there are also unknown unknowns. There are things we don't know we don't know.' (concept of serendipitous discovery)

LEADING A SESSION

Sessions are led by the participants. If you can imagine leading a session, please add your session topic proposal and your name here. In case you can only attend either the morning or the afternoon session slot, indicate this as well. Please bear in mind that it is important that you can attend the slots "Presentation of results" at 3:45pm and the "Wrap-up and Closing" of the event.

Would you like to pitch and lead a session? Excellent!

Session formats can entirely be defined by you. Maybe you are currently working on a project, article or talk, and you would like others to join writing a draft paper collaboratively? Or maybe you have a story to share on which you'd like to hear other participants' opinions? Or you'd like to put a problem up for discussion and look for solutions together? Or you have worked with a great new research discovery platform or tool that you'd like others to test likewise? Or have you ever wanted to write a manifesto about the notion of discovery in research? Or you get inspired by one of the topic ideas & wishes from above?

Whatever it is, post a suggestion here! At the beginning of the event, you will be invited to pitch your idea (30-60 seconds, depending on the number of suggestions), and participants will then vote on the topics that will actually find their way onto the agenda. Results of the group work will be captured here on the Miro board.

If you had a complete discovery portal for SSH research outcomes, how would you like to use it? What functionality would you like to find?

Difficulties in Discovery: What are your annoyances? Vent them here

Uptake of Open Science Resources in SMEs and Industry

(Preferred time slot: 11:30-13:00)

Overcoming the discoverability crisis

There's no denying: discoverability is in a crisis. With 3 million research papers published every year, alongside a growing diversity of scientific outputs such as datasets, discoverability has become a question of managing not only the magnitude of the output, but also of a plethora of resource types. In this session, we will discuss the causes and impact of this crisis, but also ways to overcome it.

Background:

<https://www.degruyter.com/document/doi/10.1515/abi-tech-2021-0003/html>

[Preferred time slot: 11:30-13:00]

What are the obstacles and challenges in offering a discovery service for a library and do they apply to Open Access resources?

(First session only)

From the point of view of an ordinary scholar: I am just interested in my research. Of course I want my results to be findable. Beside traditional publications I take care of my blog: what do I have to keep in mind when it comes to thinking of discovery systems? Optimising key words, just this?
<https://dkulog.hypotheses.org/>
Sessions II

Working with online content management systems: preferred tools, features, challenges (Sessions I) format: demo + co-design on [Google Jamboard or] Miro

(First session slot preferred)

Ideas to improve peer reviews in Scientific documents

How to disseminate and make Digital Scholarship discoverable: experiences, ideas and proposals in order to have new forms of scholarship, based on electronic publishing, more discoverable in the infosphere.
Sessions I

What are the challenges of finding reliable partners online?

What is the meaning of "discovery" in the different languages?
The goal of this session is to analyze the term in several languages, so to see how multilingualism affects the definition of the term, and its translation into practice in the different European cultures and languages

(preferred session II)

Where are we today?

Take a pin and move it to the location where you are at this moment.

De facto territorial control map of the world
 as of 14.V.2019

- BRAZIL** Sovereign independent state recognized by UN
- Guernsey (br.)** Dependent territory recognized by UN
- REPUBLIC OF CHINA** Independent state unrecognized by UN
- ROJAVA** Independent group controlling territory
- Disputed border/frontline

by u/GrzegorzusLudi 2019
 inspired by omniatlas.com and historical atlases

Source of world map: GrzegorzusLudi, [CC BY-SA 3.0](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/3.0/), via Wikimedia Commons (<https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:De-facto-territory-control-map-of-the-world-14-05-2019.svg>)

Click on the bar(s) that
apply to you. You have up
to four votes.

Which primary disciplinary background do you have?

Social Sciences & Humanities (Anthropology, Economics, Education, Geography, History, Law, Linguistics, Music, Political Science, Psychology, etc.)

36

Natural Sciences (Chemistry, Geology, Mathematics, Physics, etc.)

2

Life Sciences (Medicine, Biology, Neuroscience, Pharmacy, Zoology, etc.)

1

Engineering (Architecture, Civil Engineering, Computer Science, Electrical Engineering, Mechanical Engineering, etc.)

9

Have you ever attended a ThatCamp or BarCamp before (online or offline)?

Yes

Create a new (empty) green or red sticky note and place it in either the "Yes" or the "No" box.

No

Please vote for the topics you would like to work on (you have 8 votes):

If you had a complete discovery portal for SSH research outcomes, how would you like to use it? What functionality would you like to find?

43

How to disseminate and make Digital Scholarship discoverable: experiences, ideas and proposals in order to have new forms of scholarship, based on electronic publishing, more discoverable in the infosphere. - Sessions I

27

Difficulties in Discovery: What are your annoyances? Vent them here

34

Working with online content management systems: preferred tools, features, challenges (Sessions I); format: demo + co-design

25

Uptake of Open Science Resources in SMEs and Industry

17

What do I have to keep in mind as a researcher when it comes to thinking of discovery systems? Optimising key words, just this? <https://dkblog.hypotheses.org/>

26

Overcoming the discoverability crisis

29

Ideas to improve peer reviews in Scientific documents

34

What are the obstacles and challenges in offering a discovery service and do they apply to Open Access resources?

32

What is the meaning of "discovery" in the different languages?

31

What are the challenges of finding reliable partners online?

20

I Morning Sessions (4 parallel slots)

Room 1) How to disseminate and make Digital Scholarship discoverable: experiences, ideas and proposals in order to have new forms of scholarship, based on electronic publishing, more discoverable in the infosphere.

Room 2) Difficulties in Discovery: What are your annoyances? Vent them here

Room 3) What are the obstacles and challenges in offering a discovery service and do they apply to Open Access resources?

Room 4) Overcoming the discoverability crisis

II Afternoon Sessions (4 parallel slots)

Room 1) Ideas to improve peer reviews in Scientific documents

Room 2) What is the meaning of "discovery" in the different languages?

Room 3) If you had a complete discovery portal for SSH research outcomes, how would you like to use it? What functionality would you like to find?

Room 4) What do I have to keep in mind as a researcher when it comes to thinking of discovery systems? Optimising key words, just this?

<https://dkblog.hypotheses.org>

Session Block I - Morning Sessions

The first TRIPLE ThatCamp

11 May 2021

Room 1) How to disseminate and make Digital Scholarship discoverable:experiences, ideas and proposals in order to have new forms of scholarship, based on electronic publishing, more discoverable in the infosphere.

Scalar: an open platform for enhanced publications

Ethical issue: another level of disparity between institutions (better Scholarly Communication Offices, better digital scholarship)

HARDSHIPS ON CHANGING

Parallel scholarship: [print and online](#)

Supernational Infrastructures e.g. [Open Research Europe](#)

example of video with DOI: <https://bop.unib.e.ch/baf/article/view/7191>

How to peer review a video article?

ALL-IN-ONE: paper, tool data, code, video.

WANT: To fully leverage the possibilities of Electronic Publishing

NEED: to rethink the scholarly evaluation process

Medical video journal (with IF)

high quality educational video with a specific attention to the communication and narrative strategies: <https://www.youtube.com/user/crashcourse>

The Pyramidal Book by Robert Darton: different layers with different aims to disseminate scholarship

research evaluation as a limiting factor in innovation

true digital formats and tools

Digital preservation issue: use of open standard, structural and semantic metadata

Transmedia scholarship: the case of "Why we Post": from print scholarship to MOOC

languages of communication for inclusion?

Different sensibilities and needs in different scholarly communities (and in different generations of scholars)

sustainability

The role of Data Visualization (see Flourish)

Use of "Rabbit holes" to disseminate scholarship (see the involuntary case of Katie Bouman)

Multimodal monographs: The case of "Complex Tv Storytelling" by Jason Mittell. In progress (electronic), printed and enhanced

Room 2) Difficulties in Discovery: What are your annoyances? Vent them here

9-11 participants

Please add your name on a Post-it note

Back →
Session
Overview

Back →
Programme

What is it that annoys you most with the Discovery Process?

Difficulty finding what you need?

Information Overload?

Difficulty Accessing Data?

Difficulty making sense of what's there?

Not getting access to the resource "discovered" in the discovery system (eResource licences, etc)

Q: Would it help to have an open access marker?
A: Still there are problems to finally access the sources due to the licence packing of libraries...

Need to buy proprietary software systems. Algorithm for ranking is a black box Users should know and be able to set what's important to them. CW

the ranking of the search algorithms (black box discovery system): what is programmed in the algorithms as a "pre-assumption"

Meaning and Data for different communities. Classification of data? Will users be able to find what they are looking for?

Where does the metadata come from? (takes time until articles get listed in discovery systems)

researchers use workarounds to overcome use of different terms

History of different searches useful

I identify with the "difficulty in making sense of what is there" affirmation - depending on where you search, the results are very different and that makes more difficult to make a bibliographic review for example

How to know in what other platforms that work is also indexed or referenced. To have an idea of its discoverability in the fragmented space!

To have a standard for "openness", 90-95% of the conditions lead to not open titles

tickbox for what's important (ranking)

Solution: inform users about the ranking programming

Rights management with regard to articles (forwarding downloaded articles to colleagues/researchers) -> enough metadata is important for decision making, title only does not help

difficulty in finding projects.

Need to have an easy way to export

Instructional videos for the GoTriple Platform useful

Hard to find articles based on keywords (not sufficient linkages)

Lack of access Paywall etc. JW

Clear labelling of OA resources? ALF

How people do discovery differently.

balance between finding exactly what you need and serendipitous discovery

multilingual ontologies

Ranking should also not prioritize "famous" researchers (link to citation indexes" but should allow a search "publications in a field in the last 5 years"

Controlled vocabularies difficult to manage across disciplines

Lack of multilinguality of the discovery system is a big issue especially in non-latin scripts

explore.
openair
e.eu MB

How do we use the results of the search :
History/ Outputs

How do we manage the conflict between focussed search and serendipitous discovery?
Recommender systems

How can we allow the user be more in control?

How can we overcome the use of so many different terms Multidisciplinary / languages

How to find tools that enable the analysis of our Discoveries (Marketplace of free tools)

Lack of Open Access (or no labelling that it's not OA)

Problem - algorithms meaning that all researchers discovering the same data due to Rec Systems

systems remembering your past actions. Positive & negative

speed - Google otherwise DuckDuckGo

If you're Looking for research DATA, try it here maybe ;) :
<http://b2find.eudat.eu/dataset>

Do users want to be guided or be free to make their own choices on discovery (searches)

Using a quiz to determine the level of the user. (Binance - Crypto Trading App does this). A lot investment companies also have it to determine your risk appetite.

This looks into use cases of Researchers Looking for data: <https://zenodo.org/record/1050926>

Shows funders OA/ project. Search on many fields

Funnelling - direction chosen by past actions

nice to promote finding 'new' things

Randomize Articles similar to Wikipedia - Serendipity of research.

Room 3) What are the obstacles and challenges in offering a discovery service for a library and do they apply to a (hypothetical) Open Access discovery service ?

Room 4) Overcoming the discoverability crisis

Session Block II - Afternoon Sessions

The first TRIPLE ThatCamp

11 May 2021

Room 1) Ideas to improve peer reviews in scientific documents

For junior researchers who don't have experience but very eager to help, what would be the best way to include them?

how people read and review?

did things change because of remote work?

How to adapt peer review to different media?

goal of the improved process: to reduce the aspect of chance in publication

jrmit

lack of good incentives for reviewing

European Research Council - projects evaluation proceedings

meta-reviewer to review the reviewers

Standardization, unified publication system - but disciplinary specific

more resources should be provided by the publishers/supply side: training, collaboration, incentive

transparency, certification, openness

organize an event for reviewers and researchers, round table of reviewers, foster discussion between the two

Room 2) What is the meaning of "discovery" in the different languages?

→
What is the meaning of "discovery" in the different languages?
The goal of this session is to analyze the term in several languages, so to see how multilingualism affects the definition of the term, and its translation into practice in the different European cultures and languages

Languages: IT, SLO, CRO, SRB, PT, FR, D

ITALIAN: The precise translation of "discovery" is, in Italian, "scoperta". The term "discoverta" is an old term, not yet used, but we can find it in literature (see, for instance, G.B. Vico's New Science, and precisely "La discoverta del vero Omero" (1725).

Despite this, we've always translated the expression "discovery platform" as "piattaforma di ricerca" ("search platform", literally translating).

Croatian: they decided not to use the term "search/research". In Croatian it means uncover something new

germany: difficult to translate
Discovery (Entdecken)

Slovenia: Discovery is difficult to translate precisely. Search, browsing (filtering), there's no precise translation for the discovery itself. Word "odkritje"- means finding something new.

French: discovery is bound to knowledge (scientific discovery).
Discovery of planets (finding something new)

Serbian: it means finding something new and it is usually implied that this is new for everyone, not just to the subject. Difficult to translate. Making something discoverable: tagging, framing it. There is not direct translation. I wouldn't go for research platform: this is just searching, as this wouldn't be understood by users..
On the other hand, search platform, which is a commonly used term is not appropriate, as discovery is much more complex

Milica: we don't translate the term but explain it because we don't want to obscure or diminish its complexity.

googling the term
discovery platform, it turns out that it is a platform based on recommendation systems (wikipedia)

accessibility is connected to discoverability?

discovery platform is for curated content

Kind of a philosophical hint about discovery is that it is impossible to find a "discovery platform" that is universal and that aggregates all the content in the world. So all the discovery will always be in certain way biased (I don't like to use this word, but it is something like that)

It seems that the point is that "research" and "discovery" are issues of different stances. Focusing more on what can be added to your own experience and something that will change your pathway is indeed a discovery, not a mere search or research. It regards one's own experience.

what is the different between google and a discovery platform? It depends on the users :-)
Some people use it as a search engine and others as a discovery platform.

Discovery implies innovation? I was thinking about commercial publisher services

Portuguese: "descoberta". It also means finding something new, something that was not know before.
I didn't use this word for "researching platform" before knowing TRIPLE project.
For discovery in the meaning that we are using here I would normally use "plataforma de busca" or research platform.

librarians can help/support researchers in the discovery processes

Giordano Bruno - [theory](#)

Who can help - role of librarians / research libraries / data stewards?

what is the relation between Discovery and serendipity?

Concern: using always the same platforms impacts the research process and the results. And it is related to the training issue for researching.

Room 3) If you had a complete discovery portal for SSH research outcomes, how would you like to use it? What functionality would you like to find?

Room 4) What do I have to keep in mind as a researcher when it comes to thinking of discovery systems? Optimising key words, just this? <https://dkblog.hypotheses.org/>

Issue: metadata (researcher often just focuses on their specialty, not on the standards)

Main problem: Service in terms of metadata? Connection of one's own metadata to the library vocabularies How can the collaboration be improved?

Main groups: - scholars - librarians
Issue - attitudes Blogging as a bridging activity Getting the attention - not just accepting services

AI in TRIPLE: categories (MORESS) are applied based on the key words - currently being developed (but humans check)

Digital literacy to start asap Human-centred computer sciences Raising awareness

Important to have a bit of 'disruption', workshops with IT to discuss categories etc

How can different publications be more visible (e.g. blogs)?

Liaison person helps! Collaboration is needed Links between stakeholders

Example of a workshop: bringing different people together

Cataloguing/classification to be done by researchers?? - complex systems of catalogues (e.g. linking things) - topic of automating the description

Time as a resource - important for researchers (Academia/Researchgate easier to operate) "I am the owner who is responsible" Librarians to explain why metadata is important

Open access as something specific, not just posting something on the web

research software developers important as well! - converting needs to technical solutions

Problem with Google - how we know that this blog will be found

FUNDING: data sharing important

Librarians to share knowledge and ask questions

Potential clashes - e.g. how to organise the data

standardised vs. free vocabulary

Open science often listed as 'innovation' by researchers Important to have direct communication Good to see close ties developing between groups

Britta - experience in providing admin and technical support to blogging researchers

the library system to be needs-oriented / bridging research and infrastructure needs Classification systems as too slow to catch up? Free keywords are used by researchers

more qualitative description of text (e.g. blog)

IDEA FOR TRIPLE: Testing AI for TRIPLE, talking the classifications +beta users

had to get rid of the old catalogue and more experienced researchers hate the discovery service because it is not very precise

completely separate but there are ways for more relationships between different information in the catalogue

Visibility as a hot topic at an institution e.g. how to enhance a blog post before handing over a text to the library

Conclusions: - liaison person between libraries and scholars (close contact + exchange needs) + research software developers - joined workshops for different groups

<https://dkblog.hypotheses.org/>

Feedback Area

Feel free to add any feedback here that comes to your mind during the event. We're also going to do a short event evaluation via Zoom during the last session today.

What do you like about the event?

The strong female presence is really amazing =)

Very well organised and great introductions to the tool - it worked very well!

very good organization and nice the MIRO tool! Thank you

How can we improve the format of upcoming TRIPLE ThatCamp events?

The dream would be that the next one is in person!

Are there any specific topics that would you like to see presented in future TRIPLE webinars/trainings/workshops?

I think that for the major public it would be nice to have a opening session explaining more about the functioning of GOTRIPLE and the status of it in the moment of the event

a focus on training: i.e. what are the more effective methodologies and tools for training reserachers in digital literacy

Do you have any further comments?

I would like to keep in touch with the participants (such interesting people I met today!). If anyone is interested in our work at CNR Bologna: <https://linktr.ee/bibliocrba>